

Table 6: Consensus ranking of the statements

Stmt. No.	Consensus statements – Those that do not distinguish between any pair of factors Statement	Ranking in the different themes			Consensus Rank
		Intrinsically Motivated	Altruistic Leaning	Sales vs. Fiduciary	
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature of their workload because it might discourage getting new referrals.	2	2	2	1
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my boss.	-4	-4	-4	2
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad financial planning topics.	-1	-1	-1	3
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not reasonable, it is demotivating.	1	1	2	4
32	PCAs should be allowed to ‘soft-close’ and /or reopen their practice as desired based upon workload.	1	0	2	5
13	I must keep in mind as important, that clients equate inactivity with their advisor ‘being asleep at the wheel’.	-1	-1	1	6
24	Sometimes an employees’ contribution to the firm’s business is not fully reflected in their production numbers.	2	4	1	7
9	PCAs may be reluctant to ‘fire’ a client because of the damage it may cause to their relationship with the referring FC.	2	0	3	8
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I didn’t have specific, measurable performance expectations.	0	1	0	9
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose focus on sales may require me to work with clients for whom the PCIA offer may not be well suited.	1	3	1	10
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting client concerns about portfolio performance.	0	0	-2	11
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may sometimes make me think twice about disagreeing with a client or delivering news that might be perceived negatively.	-1	-3	-3	12
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specific, measurable performance targets.	0	-1	-2	13

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		Intrinsically Motivated	Altruistic Leaning	Sales vs. Fiduciary	
		29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to compromise my ethical standards at least a little.	-2	-2
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about individual PCA investor portfolio performance.	-3	-2	-5	15
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the performance of their investments.	0	1	-1	16
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cover the same branch locations.	1	4	2	17
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and which ones to remove from my practice.	-2	-5	-4	18
35	My success depends on getting new referrals from FCs so I should be careful not to contradict or alienate them.	0	2	3	19
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and single-topic solutions provides a desirable way to motivate me.	-3	-2	-2	20
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed.	-1	0	-2	21
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succeed.	-2	0	-3	22
19	As long as I were well paid, if I didn't have performance targets, I would be motivated anyway because I find the work I do is important and personally gratifying.	4	1	1	23
36	I feel my role is sales-oriented because I have to sell myself to FCs and sell myself to clients.	2	2	5	24
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box' mentality where the quality of the work can be secondary to getting it done.	3	2	4	25
21	If we were really 'looking through client's eyes', it would be best to tie bonuses to how well clients are doing toward achieving their financial goals.	1	3	-1	26
12	I must keep in mind, as important, that clients equate trading activity with progress.	0	-2	1	27

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		Intrinsically	Altruistic	Sales vs.	Rank
		Motivated	Leaning	Fiduciary	
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive.	-3	-4	0	28
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and single-topic solutions clients receive.	-5	-3	-1	29
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they would receive adequate attention if they knew I have responsibility for 185 clients.	3	-1	3	30
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how well I serve clients.	-4	-3	0	31
3	Because of my workload, I sometimes worry about the possibility of important things falling through the cracks.	4	0	4	32
31	As a fiduciary, I have too many clients to serve them all well.	5	3	0	33
34	It is awkward when a client asks, "How often do you review my investments?" because the real answer may not seem like it would be often enough to them.	3	-1	-1	34
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company performed.	-2	1	-3	35
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investors succeed as possible.	-1	5	0	36